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Multi-Purpose COTS-based Edge AI Computing Platform for Selective Compression in Small Satellites

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Abstract

Due to the constrained computational capabilities of small satellites and the size and complexity of Earth observation data, most processing is performed on the ground. This situation requires the downlink of the full or almost full set of data recorded by the satellite, which imposes high data storage and downlink bandwidth requirements on the mission. Example situations include ground cover analysis, ship detection, Earth imaging and spectral imaging. Each of these scenarios include the collection of many gigabytes of data to be transmitted down to ground. As sensor resolutions improve, so too grows the amount of data that needs transmitting.

However, this downlink from satellite to ground station is constrained. Small satellites typically only have one dedicated ground station, which can only be accessed once per orbit for an extremely limited amount of time. In taking this approach, a multitude of problematic factors impact the amount of data that can be communicated. Factors such as power constraints, heat dissipation design limits, the downlink communication bandwidth, energy budget constraints and the fact that launch factors (such as deviation from the ideal orbit) can affect the availability of the ground station to the satellite.

Artificial Intelligence (AI) provides a potential approach for mitigating these problems. It has the ability to interpret images in-orbit, thereby reducing the in-orbit data storage requirements or reducing the necessary downlink budget. For example, an input image can be cropped to only its point of interest (ship detection) or images can be converted into descriptions or labels. Transmitting only these labels or cropped datasets will require magnitudes less downlink bandwidth compared to the complete data. Furthermore, this approach also opens the way to data storage decisions being made on-board, such as in the case of cloud detection (where Earth images mostly covered by clouds are discarded). Proven AI algorithms for processing these datasets already exist but are typically only applied on the ground. Power and energy efficient AI inference requires the usage of specialized hardware, an AI accelerator. AI accelerators can be application specific or multi-purpose, which both come with strengths and weaknesses.

For smaller missions it is not always feasible or cost-effective to develop a specialized AI accelerator that is only effective for one neural network or mission. As such, there is a need for a generic and multi-purpose AI accelerator platform for on-board edge computing in space applications. This module must be reconfigurable (in terms of neural network), low-power (a peak power below 20W) and low-energy consumption with the ability to pre-process input data.

To achieve the goal of a widely applicable, multi-purpose and generic AI platform, selection of commercial off-the-shelf (COTS) components is performed. With the components being selected on clear metrics such

as computational performance and efficiency, radiation hardness, peak power consumption, thermal design power, die area, chip availability and software support.

The scenario used to evaluate the effectiveness of this approach is based around a demonstration AI algorithm which implements selective compression on remote sensing data of ships in the ocean. It crops the image data to only the areas of interest, which in this case are the ships. Furthermore, to support this evaluation, the AOPU is also tested in conjunction with several common image classification and detection neural networks.

In this paper we present a multi-purpose AI On-board Processing Unit (AOPU) built from COTS parts that can be reused for multiple projects. The unit has been tested for radiation robustness and has been tested with common neural network models. The results from these tests show that this AOPU is a promising candidate for AI applications such as selective compression. For future work, we aim to test the unit in proton testing and explore several other use cases such as vegetation or land cover identification.

1 INTRODUCTION

There are many use-cases where remote sensing through the use of satellites is crucial. Missions such as Earth observation, vegetation or land cover identification and surveillance are some of these purposes [1, 2, 3]. These missions are achieved through a variety of sensors with various resolutions and pixel depths, both of which are growing day by day [4]. This increase in resolutions results in more and more data being produced in orbit during the operation of these spacecraft. Although storage has grown to support these data sizes, downlink bandwidth capabilities of many satellites and ground stations have not grown at the same rate.

One method of tackling this problem is the use of compression of the to be transmitted data so that it may still fit within the bandwidth restraints enforced on the system. Compression can take many forms and in a number of cases, selective compression can help solve the issues associated with the data sizes of modern satellite technology [5]. An example of selective compression in a real world application would be in the case of ship detection, where the detected ship and associated features are deemed most interesting and the rest of the image is either highly compressed or discarded entirely [1, 6, 7].

To implement selective compression in such a use-case, one possible avenue is to employ Artificial Intelligence (AI) to interpret images and select which parts of the data are worth maintaining or transmitting uncompressed and which parts should be highly compressed or discarded. AI by way of deep learning (DL) can be trained with data sets to recognize features of interesting data [8]. This training can be performed prior to deployment, with only inference occurring in the satellite. Only transmitting the of-interest data downstream can save significant amounts of bandwidth. In order to facilitate a satellite that can operate in this way, an AI hardware platform and matching AI model must be designed. However, for smaller missions and satellites, it is not always feasible or cost-effective to design bespoke hardware for one mission or one neural network [9]. This means that there is a need for a hardware platform that can support multiple missions and AI configurations.

This paper proposes a fully integrated solution, AI On-board Processing Unit (AOPU). This is an AI hardware platform built with COTS designed specifically to enable deep learning applications such as those used in selective compression algorithms. This forgoes specialized AI solutions, but instead focuses on a reusable which can be used in the use-case with which it will be demonstrated with in this paper, but also other missions which required on-board AI for data compression purposes. The full system is also tested for operation under space conditions through TID (Total Ionizing Dose) testing. Proton testing is forthcoming.

2 HARDWARE PLATFORM

Traditional embedded systems hardware generally cannot support AI applications under the restraints characteristic of satellite and other space missions [10, 11]. Thus creating a necessity for a hardware platform specific to the application of running DL applications in space under space constraints. For many projects, it is not feasible to design bespoke hardware for AI applications for a given mission. Custom hardware is costly and time consuming.

Thus, we propose the AOPU, a fully integrated design which is meant to be generically applicable for AI image processing and AI compression applications. To demonstrate the capabilities of this hardware platform and its usefulness in space applications, it is shown performing an AI model for the on-board selective compression

of satellite imagery. To complement this demonstration and to show the generic applicability of the hardware platform, several other AI models are also shown performing in section 4.

2.1 HARDWARE REQUIREMENTS

For the hardware platform to be suitable to the type of missions it is designed for, the platform must be a) robust against radiation, b) capable of performing the AI model within specified constraints of power consumption and processing speed. The requirements set for this design are a maximum power consumption of 10W and processing at at least 2 fps for the selected demonstration mission (of selective compression in ship detection).

The high-level design requirements are as follows:

1. The unit shall have an expected lifetime in space of 5 years (with a minimum of 2 years)
2. Expected orbit is LEO (Low Earth Orbit)
3. The size shall be approximately $\frac{1}{2}$ U, with a mass of not more than 1 kg
4. The TID it should withstand (possibly after shielding) should be at least 5 krad
5. The targeted power consumption is 10W, with no peak higher than 20W
6. An up-time of 98%
7. A computational target of 7-8 TOPS (Tera Operations Per Second)

This list is non-exhaustive and describes the most core high-level requirements of the hardware platform. Other requirements include the amount of RAM necessary, the amount of storage for science data and other implementation details. These requirements were derived from a co-design process with the demonstration selective compression AI algorithm further described in section 4. The final hardware platform consists of a fully integrated solution which is built with COTS components. It will handle the AI processing, pre- and post-processing of the data, housekeeping and all relevant memory operations.

3 SOFTWARE ARCHITECTURE

Fig. 1: High-level representation of the software architecture.

Figure 1 shows the high-level structure of the software architecture. To facilitate interaction between the AI processor, imaging sensor and memory units a software architecture is designed to facilitate straightforward usage of the entire platform. This software architecture allows the end-user of the mission to integrate the solution into their mission design seamlessly. Only needing to add the AI model to be performed for complete functionality.

3.1 PIPELINE RECONFIGURABILITY

The software architecture is designed in such a way that it facilitates in-flight exchangeable AI models. The core pipeline of the AOPU’s software consists of input data pre-processing, AI processing or inference and finally image post-processing. The AI processing layer in the pipeline supports popular deep learning frameworks such as TensorFlow, TensorFlow Lite and ONNX.

For example, in the scenario that your current model has been superseded by a new model that also fits the mission and an update is desired. It not only allows for updating the AI model when necessary but also allows for a complete change of the method of data analysis or compression. The software also implements a virtual pipeline, which is what allows for reconfigurability of the pre- and post-processing layers. The user can define the pre-processing and post-processing steps and dedicate computational units to their execution.

4 DEEP LEARNING IMPLEMENTATION

This section covers the ship detection use case and computational performance for various neural network models.

4.1 DEEP LEARNING BENCHMARKS

To further demonstrate the capabilities of the system, the AOPU was also tested with different neural network models common to on-board space-based applications. These tests are focused on the frames per second (fps) and RAM (DDR in MB) usage when inferring on an image in a variety of large neural networks. The results of these tests are shown in Table 1. The different resolutions of the mobileNetV1 and regNetX was selected to better understand how the input image resolution affects the latency and memory usage. The mobileNet networks are focused on object detection, and the regNetX models implement an image classification neural network.

As can be seen in Table 1 as the input image resolutions increase, the larger the latency and memory usage. These results indicate that, the AI processor is sufficient enough for inference of different network models compared to the requirement of the project. However, it also indicates that another computation unit is needed for the preprocessing stage.

Table 1: Performance results from different networks run on the hardware.

Network	Input Image Size	FPS	Inference time	DDR usage
ONR-CL-6060-mobileNetV1	224 x 224 pixels	635,06	1,57 ms	3,35 MB
ONR-CL-6062-mobileNetV1	1024 x 1024 pixels	98,81	10,12 ms	18,84 MB
ONR-CL-6072-mobileNetV1	1024 x 1024 pixels	92,63	10,80 ms	21,89 MB
ONR-CL-6142-regNetX-1.6gf	1024 x 1024 pixels	34,76	28,76 ms	63,78 MB
ONR-CL-6141-regNetX-1.6gf	512 x 512 pixels	109,59	9,12 ms	18,12 MB
ONR-CL-6121-regNetX-400mf	512 x 512 pixels	189,64	5,27 ms	11,65 MB

4.2 SHIP DETECTION SELECTIVE COMPRESSION ALGORITHM

To validate the hardware platform as useful for the implementation of AI selective compression in real world missions, a ship detection and classification algorithm is demonstrated. The algorithm is currently still a work in progress, and modifications are expected before a final algorithm is presented. The algorithm is co-designed. This trained algorithm will be able to classify ships on imagery and determine the exact location and size (in the image) of the ship. By using this, the image can then be cropped or compressed with spatial priorities to reduce bandwidth needed to transmit the useful data downstream.

This trained algorithm will be used to selectively compress Earth observation imagery based on its classification results. Performing such a classification is much less computationally intensive compared to the training procedure and is therefore suitable for on-board processing.

Fig. 2: An example of a full pre-processed image from the sensor, with the AI's selection inference results displayed.

Fig. 3: The cropped selected ship, which is actually saved to memory and eventually transmitted.

In an example usage of this selective compression algorithm to compress the image shown in Figure 2, the algorithm selects all the ships, their sizes and their locations. This allows us to crop the image to only this part of the image. This results in a compression ratio of a whopping 3.2% (as the image goes from an area of 589K pixels, to only 19K pixels).

4.2.1 AI ARCHITECTURE

The source input images are of a size of 7150x5750 pixels, with a 12 bits pixel depth. Each image is sliced into parts of 1000x1000 pixels. The AI model's base structure is a YOLOv5 (You Only Look Once) architecture, which is a family of models for object detection which is pretrained on a dataset of images. This model is then further trained on images of scenes with ships based on a Sentinel-2 image dataset. YOLOv5 is a Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) with a number of convolutional layers which converge to a classification. Aside from further training, the model has also been converted into a format (ONNX) compatible with the AI processor on the hardware platform. The algorithm is the most current version of an algorithm first developed on YOLOv3 and has been tested on a number of different platforms.

4.2.2 IMAGE PRE-PROCESSING

To go from sensor data to data that can be interpreted by the AI image pre-processing is required. The pre-processing steps include decompression, orthorectification, radiometric corrections and resampling. These steps are generally referred to as processing data to Level-1C, as seen in Figure 4.

The pre-processing stage starts with Level 0 where it first gets processed through a MSI telemetry analysis. This step retrieves the instrument source data and performs data analysis and error correction. The next is to stamp each image line with an exact capture time of each instrument source data packet. Then the low-resolution image extraction happens, where the low resolution image is extracted for quicklook generation. The last step of level 0 is satellite ancillary telemetry analysis where the collected bit values gets compared to pre-defined ranges. Level 1 is split into A, B, and C where more intense processing is performed on the decompressed data. These steps are preferably not to be computed on an AI processor, as these tasks are more diverse. Thus the pre-processing (and post-processing) steps are performed on another computational device incorporated in the solution.

Fig. 4: Typical pre-processing pipeline, with the AI model used in this demonstrator using data from level 1C

5 RADIATION HARDNESS

As electronic components are exposed to harsh radiation heavy environments during satellite missions, the system must be robust to radiation to be qualified for most usage scenarios. In the case of negative effects from the radiation, additional shielding may be applied.

5.1 Test Setup

The test setup had the components which required testing mounted in front of the particle beam with data cables running out of the room towards a measurement setup in the adjacent room. Here data was collected all throughout the irradiation process, data regarding the voltages and operation of the devices.

During the test, AOPU was running several software benchmarks that were focused on testing the hardware peripherals of the unit such as Ethernet, CAN-bus, USB, Camera Serial Interface (CSI), and I2C. On top of that, it was running a test AI network to better understand how the AI processor gets affected by TID testing. The CAN-bus was connected to another MCU to give a standard reply back for every can message. The I2C bus was connected to temperature and humidity sensor. The CSI interface was connected to a camera and the raw data from the camera was collected during the test. The setup also includes monitoring all voltage supplies on the AOPU board. The data from the software tests were stored in two ways. The first path was via Ethernet where it logged the internal event and date to an external computer. The other path was through a USB-drive that was outside the radiation chamber. These two ways of logging data ensured that if the USB-driver stopped working, the Ethernet would log it and vice versa. The AUPO also ran different memory tests that were focused on classifying RAM speed, bandwidth, throughput and finding memory faults.

It was tested to a maximum dose of 515 Gy over the course of 6 days. Over the course of each day the dosage increased 3.793 Gy per hour.

Fig. 5: A sketch showing the setup during testing.

Fig. 6: A photograph of the setup during testing, showing the source of the beam and the mounted board.

5.2 RADIATION RESULTS

The system showed robustness at the doses it was exposed to with no temporary or permanent effects seen. The logged data of all the software tests did not indicate any damage or distribution of functionality. The hardware peripherals such as CAN, I2C, CSI, Ethernet, and USB of the unit operated without errors. The AI processor with the test network produced the same results as the start of the test. The other software benchmarks did also not indicate any faults or reduced accuracy. Future planned tests include proton testing.

6 CONCLUSION

In conclusion, we present an AI computing platform for selective compression with reusability in mind. Firstly, we explored a ship detection use case to illustrate how the AOPU can be used for selective compression. This case covers both pre-processing and the actually AI inference. The AI inference stage is based on a YOLOV5 architecture, while the pre-processing stage converts sensor data to Sentinel Level-1C. Secondly, to better understand the AI capabilities of the system, the AOPU were tested with different neural networks such as mobileNetV1 and regNetX. These tests were more focused on computational performance such as FPS and memory usage, than accuracy. The purpose is to show that the platform can be used for different network models. Thirdly, to use the AOPU in space, we need to demonstrate some degree of radiation robustness. The AOPU has gone through TID testing and had was exposed to maximum does of 515 Gy over 6 days. This unit survived the test without any issues.

As future work, we plan to further explore the radiation robustness by performing proton testing on the AOPU unit. We also seek to explore alternative use-cases such as truck detection, crops/vegation, cloud detection, and more.

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